

GREEN SYNTHESIS AND PHYSICOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF CURCUMIN-LOADED SILVER NANOPARTICLES: OPTIMIZATION AND SELECTION OF NANOFORMULATIONS (F6 AND F8) FOR TOPICAL GEL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Curcumin exhibits a wide range of biological activities such as antioxidant, antifungal, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antitumor, antiviral and wound healing effect. However, It has poor solubility in water and low bioavailability. Silver nanoparticles display interesting properties for applications in nanomedicine due to their ability to enhance biological activity. **Objective:** The aim of the study is to synthesize and characterize curcumin-loaded silver nanoparticles (Cur-Ag NPs) and optimize a suitable formulation for topical application. **Method:** Nine formulations (F1-F9) of Cur-Ag NPs were prepared by Green synthesis Approach. These formulations were evaluated for Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) using UV-Visible Spectroscopy, Particle Size Distribution (PSD), and Zeta Potential. The formulations that were selected were subjected to further Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) and X-ray Diffraction (XRD) testing; this decision was, based on the particle/ nanoscale size and colloidal stability. Four topical formulations such as petrolatum-based ointment (TF1), PEG-based ointment (TF2), cream (TF3), and gel (TF4) containing 1% Cur-Ag NPs were prepared using suitable excipients and evaluated for appearance, homogeneity, pH and rheology. **Results:** UV-visible spectroscopy analysis revealed SPR peaks at 438–467 nm for F1–F8, confirming silver nanoparticle formation. However, F9 exhibited a peak at 223 nm, indicating no typical Cur-Ag NPs formation. Among these nine formulations, F6 and F8 showed optimal PSD with D90 values between 100 and 200 nm and zeta potential values greater than +30 mV, indicating excellent colloidal stability. These formulations were selected for structural and crystalline characterization using TEM and XRD. All Four topical formulations were stable and homogeneous. TF3 (pH 5.12) and TF4 (pH 7.21) showed suitable skin compatibility, indicating their suitability for topical application. All formulations exhibited shear-thinning behaviour, with ointments TF1 and TF2 showing higher yield stress (43–61 Pa) than cream TF3 and gel TF4 (~1–2 Pa), indicating greater flow resistance. **Conclusion:** Cur-Ag NPs were successfully developed. F6 and F8 demonstrated desirable physicochemical characteristics, making them promising candidates for incorporation into topical gel formulations. All four topical formulations showed good physicochemical properties and skin-compatible pH, suggesting their potential for topical application. Ointments TF1 and TF2 have lower spreadability, whereas cream TF3 and gel TF4 are easier to apply, reflecting formulation-dependent rheological properties. Future work will focus on in vivo animal studies.

Keywords: Curcumin, Silver nanoparticles, synthesis, characterization.

INTRODUCTION

Nanoparticles are particles with sizes ranging from 1 to 100 nm. Both metallic and non-metallic nanoparticles within this size range are commonly used for antibacterial purposes. Various metal nanoparticles (such as Ag, Cu, Au, Pt, Zn, and Mg) and metal oxide nanoparticles (including TiO₂, Ag₂O, and ZnO) have shown substantial therapeutic potential in medical applications. Furthermore, metallic nanoparticles are extensively applied in biosensing, diagnostic imaging, and drug delivery systems. [1,2,3]

Curcumin is a natural yellow–orange diphenolic compound obtained from the dried rhizomes of *Curcuma longa*, a member of the Zingiberaceae family. It is widely recognized for its wound-healing properties and exhibits anti-inflammatory, anti-angiogenic, anti-carcinogenic, and antioxidant activities. It absorbs blue light in the 400–500 nm range and generates ROS in the presence of molecular oxygen. However, curcumin has poor water solubility and limited bioavailability. However, its stability and bioavailability can be enhanced by conjugating it with metal nanoparticles. [4,5,6,7,8,9,10]

Silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs) have gained significant interest in scientific research due to their wide range of applications in fields such as engineering, medicine, chemistry, and physics. Their small size (1–100 nm) allows them to interact with biological systems at the molecular level, which enhances their effectiveness in nanomedicine. Advancements in nanotechnology have enabled the development of silver nanoparticles as a novel therapeutic approach. Owing to their broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity, Ag NPs are widely used in biomedical applications, particularly in wound care management. Among the various methods for synthesizing Ag NPs, green synthesis using natural sources such as plant extracts has attracted considerable attention because it is safe, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly. [5,11,12,13]

Ag NPs do not readily penetrate human skin and are therefore used as safe preservatives in various cosmetic and industrial products. The size and shape of Ag NPs are strongly influenced by the choice of stabilizing or capping agents, and numerous materials have been reported for their surface functionalization. Ag NPs can be synthesized using physical and chemical methods, which are generally categorized as either top-down or bottom-up approaches. However, physical methods are costly and require advanced equipment, while chemical methods often involve toxic reagents and are not environmentally friendly. To overcome these limitations, green synthesis methods have been developed to produce Ag NPs without the use of hazardous chemicals. Compared to conventional techniques, green chemistry approaches are simpler, faster, more sustainable, and environmentally benign. These advantages have encouraged extensive research into the use of biological resources for nanoparticle synthesis. [2,14,15,16,17]

Green-synthesized Ag NPs, particularly those derived from plant sources, are well known for their strong antimicrobial activity against a wide range of bacterial and fungal pathogens. Beyond healthcare applications, Ag NPs are also utilized in textiles, food packaging, surface coatings, and water purification systems.[18]

In topical drug delivery, nanoparticles have been developed as carriers for transdermal administration to improve the treatment of inflammatory conditions. Various nanoparticle-based systems have been designed to enhance skin penetration, increase drug stability, and, in some cases, provide controlled release of active compounds. Additionally, topical application of Ag NPs has been shown to support wound healing while minimizing scar formation. [19,20]

The present study focuses on the green synthesis of Cur-Ag NPs and their characterization by using analytical techniques such as ultraviolet visible spectroscopy (UV-vis spectroscopy), Particle Size Distribution (PSD), Zeta Potential, transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and X-ray diffractometry (XRD). These all cumulate in the identification of specifically optimized formulas that has been fully characterised and that are suitable for topological topical development application and the formulas respective character assessment.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

MATERIAL

Curcumin was kindly provided as a gift sample by Arjuna Natural Pvt. Ltd. (Tamil Nadu, India). Silver nitrate was sourced from Sigma-Aldrich. Glucose monohydrate, sodium hydroxide, glycerin, and disodium EDTA were obtained from Merck.

Butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) and chlorobutanol were purchased from Spectrum Chemical. Mineral oil and petrolatum were supplied by Penreco, while polyethylene glycol (PEG 1450) and PEG 300 were procured from Clariant.

Cetyl alcohol, stearic acid, isopropyl myristate, and glyceryl monostearate were acquired from BASF. Tween 80 was obtained from Croda International, and propylene glycol was purchased from Avantor. Phenoxyethanol was sourced from Ashland Global Holdings.

Carbomer homopolymer was supplied by Lubrizol Corporation. All chemicals and reagents used in this study were of analytical grade and utilized as received without any further purification.

INSTRUMENTATION

Sample preparation was carried out using a magnetic stirrer (Remi, models 5MLH and 2MLH). UV-visible spectroscopic analysis was performed with a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu Corporation, model UV-1800). Particle size and zeta potential were determined using a Litesizer 500 instrument from Anton Paar.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) studies were performed at the National Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research (NIPER), Hyderabad, using a Panalytical Empyrean 3 diffractometer. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis was carried out at Jamia Hamdard University, New Delhi, using a Thermo Scientific™ Talos L120C instrument.

The pH of the prepared formulations was measured using a pH meter (Hanna Instruments, model HI5221). Rheological characterization was conducted using an MCR 302 rheometer from Anton Paar.

SYNTHESIS OF CURCUMIN SILVER NANOPARTICLES

Silver nitrate was used as a precursor for the formation of silver nanoparticles. Required quantity of silver nitrate and Glucose monohydrate were taken in 100 mL of de-ionized water and stirred for uniformity. In another beaker, required quantity of Curcumin was taken in Ethanol and dissolved under stirring. Curcumin phase was added to the silver nitrate phase drop-wise under stirring. Yellow colored solution was observed. Then, pH was adjusted between 8 and 8.5 to obtain dark brown colored solution, indicating the formation of Cur-AgNPs. Nine formulations (F1-F9) were prepared by varying batch size, AgNO₃ concentration, glucose concentration, stirring speed, temperature, and stirring duration are depicted in Table 1.

Table 1: Composition and preparation parameters of Cur-Ag NPs formulations

Formulations	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
B. size	100mL	50mL	100mL						
Curcumin (mg)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Ag NO ₃ (mg)	17 (0.1M)	17 (0.1M)	29.25	42.5 (0.25M)	17 (0.1M)	17 (0.1M)	17 (0.1M)	17 (0.1M)	17 (0.1M)
Glucose. H ₂ O (mg)	39.63	39.63	39.63	39.63	57.94	76.26	39.63	0	39.63
NaOH	Adjusted to 8-8.5								
Stirring speed	550	550	630-650	630-650	>800	>800	>800	>800	>800
Temp during stirring	25	25	25	25	25	25	50	25	25
Stirring duration	150 min	30 min	160min	120min	180min	180min	180min	180min	180min

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CHARACTERIZATION OF CURCUMIN SILVER NANOPARTICLES

UV-VISIBLE SPECTROSCOPY

UV–visible spectroscopy is routinely used to confirm the formation of Ag NPs due to the characteristic surface plasmon resonance (SPR) phenomenon, which arises from the collective oscillation of conduction electrons in response to incident light. For silver nanoparticles, this SPR band typically appears in the range of 400–500 nm and provides qualitative information regarding nanoparticle shape and size. [21,22,28]

UV–visible spectra of all nine Cur-Ag NPs formulations (F1–F8) exhibited distinct surface plasmon resonance bands in the range of 438-467 nm, confirming the successful reduction of silver ions and the formation of Cur-Ag NPs. In contrast, formulation F9 showed an absorption band at 223 nm, which does not correspond to the typical SPR of Cur-Ag NPs. As to why F9 could have created the successful reduction of silver ions with no glucose in solution there is not a concrete reason, but what most likely occurred is that Curcumin is not acting solely as a spectator molecule and at the alkaline pH from 8-8.5 its phenolic hydroxyl groups and β -diketone moiety give it a mild reducing capacity. Therefore, the reduction of the Ag⁺ to Ag⁰ would have been possible while curcumin was coating the nascent silver nuclei thereby serving as a stabilizer and preventing aggregation. This dual role of curcumin of both a capper and a reducer has been observed before.[6] The observed SPR peak positions for all formulations are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: SPR peak values of Cur-Ag NPs formulations

Formulations	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
SPR using UV Visible Spectrophotometry (nm)	438	439	451	456	467	466	446	451	223

Overall, the UV–visible analysis confirms successful nanoparticle synthesis in F1–F8, while F9 did not demonstrate spectral evidence of metallic nanoparticle formation.

PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION (PSD)

The particle size distribution of formulations F1–F9 was determined using Litesizer 500 instrument from Anton Paar. The percentile diameters D10, D50, and D90 represent the particle size below which 10%, 50%, and 90% of particles are present, respectively and together provide valuable insight into the breadth of the particle size distribution and wide differences between these percentiles can indicate significant polydispersity or aggregation. [23,24]

Lipid nanoparticles with mean sizes around ~200 nm have been successfully developed for topical delivery to the dermis and hair follicles, demonstrating that nanoparticle sizes in the ~200 nm range are suitable for dermal therapeutic applications.[25] The observed PSD for all formulations are depicted in Table 3.

Table 3: Particle Size Distribution (PSD) values of Cur-Ag NPs formulations

Formulations	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
PSD – D10 (nm)	20.04	29.14	293.4	106.01	49.35	61.16	8.75	23.06	46.3
PSD – D50 (nm)	35.29	71.02	569.6	623.6	75.7	91.5	14.08	35.11	64.74
PSD – D90 (nm)	341	1272.2	899.3	1009.6	222.56	207.1	590.82	126.65	134.25

Most formulations (F1, F2, F5, F6, F7, F8, and F9) showed D10 values within the nanoscale range (<100 nm), confirming initial nanoparticle formation. F7 (8.75 nm) exhibited the smallest particle fraction, indicating rapid nucleation. F1 and F8 (~20–23 nm) demonstrated fine nanoparticle formation. F3 (293.4 nm) showed a significantly higher D10 value, indicating that even the smallest fraction contains large particles, suggesting poor size control.

D50 represents the median particle size and gives a better understanding of the overall formulation size. F7 (14.08 nm) showed the smallest median size. F1 (35.29 nm) and F8 (35.11 nm) demonstrated uniform nano-sized distribution. F5, F6, and F9 (64–91 nm) remained within the acceptable nanoscale range. F3 (569.6 nm) and F4 (623.6 nm) exhibited extremely high median sizes, indicating aggregation and instability. Formulations with D50 below 200 nm are generally suitable for topical and biomedical applications.

D90 indicates the upper size boundary and is critical for detecting aggregation. F8 (126.65 nm) and F9 (134.25 nm) showed the most acceptable D90 values, remaining below 200 nm. F5 (222.56 nm) and F6 (207.1 nm) were slightly above 200 nm but still near acceptable limits. F1 (341 nm), F7 (590.82 nm), F3 (899.3 nm), F4 (1009.6 nm), and F2 (1272.2 nm) exhibited very high D90 values, indicating broad distribution and significant aggregation. Overall, Size Distribution evaluation F8 and F9 are the most uniform and stable formulations. F5 and F6 are moderately acceptable formulations.

ZETA POTENTIAL

Zeta potential is a critical parameter was determined for formulations using Litesizer 500 instrument from Anton Paar. It is used to evaluate the surface charge and colloidal stability of nanoparticle dispersions. It reflects the magnitude of electrostatic repulsion between particles in suspension. Nanoparticles with high absolute zeta potential values (generally $\geq \pm 30$ mV) are considered physically stable due to strong electrostatic repulsion, which prevents aggregation. In contrast, lower absolute values indicate reduced stability and a greater tendency for particle agglomeration. [21,26] The observed Zeta Potential for all formulations are depicted in Table 4.

Table 4: Zeta potential values of Cur-Ag NPs formulations

Formulations	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Zeta Potential (mV)	-36.2	-46.7	-37.7	-36.2	-28.9	-36.8	-28	-35.3	-45.5

Most formulations exhibited negative surface charges, ranging from -28.0 mV to -46.7 mV. Formulations F1, F2, F3, F4, F6, F8, and F9 demonstrated absolute zeta potential values greater than 30 mV, indicating good colloidal stability. In contrast, F5 and F7 showed values below -30 mV, suggesting comparatively lower electrostatic stabilization.

These Formulations F1, F2, F3, F4, F6, F8, and F9 shows high absolute values indicate sufficient electrostatic repulsion between particles, thereby minimizing aggregation and enhancing dispersion stability. Among all formulations, F9 (-45.5 mV) and F2 (-46.7 mV) showed the highest magnitude of surface charge, suggesting excellent stabilization.

In contrast, F5 (-28.9 mV) and F7 (-28.0 mV) showed slightly lower absolute values, which may increase the likelihood of particle aggregation over time. It has been reported that nanoparticles with zeta potential values below ± 30 mV are more prone to agglomeration due to insufficient repulsive forces.

Overall, most formulations exhibited absolute zeta potential values greater than 30 mV, indicating good electrostatic repulsion and satisfactory colloidal stability. In contrast, F5 and F7 showed slightly lower absolute values, suggesting comparatively moderate stability.

Based on the comprehensive evaluation, formulations F6 and F8 were selected for further characterization of XRD and TEM analysis, as their PSD (D90) values were within the desired 100–200 nm range and their zeta potential values exceeded 30 mV, indicating good electrostatic stability of the nanoformulations. Although F9 also demonstrated acceptable particle size

distribution and high zeta potential, it was not selected due to its atypical SPR peak at 223 nm, which falls outside the characteristic range (400–500 nm) reported for silver nanoparticles.

TRANSMISSION ELECTRON MICROSCOPY (TEM)

TEM was useful tool to evaluate the desired size, shape, and structure of NPs at high resolution. The particle size determined by TEM was smaller than that obtained from DLS analysis. This difference arises because DLS measures the hydrodynamic diameter of nanoparticles in dispersion, including the solvation layer and surface-bound molecules, whereas TEM provides the actual core size in the dry state. [14, 27,28] TEM image of F6 and F8 are shown in figure 1 and 2 respectively.

TEM micrograph of F6 revealed predominantly spherical nanoparticles with slight aggregation. The particle size was estimated to be in the range of approximately 15–35 nm, confirming nanoscale formation. TEM micrograph of F8 showed well-defined spherical nanoparticles with particle sizes ranging approximately from 10–25 nm. The particles appeared relatively uniform with limited aggregation. Overall, the TEM findings confirmed the successful formation of nanosized Cur-Ag NPs in formulations F6 and F8, supporting for further crystallographic analysis by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), and subsequent topical application studies.

Figure1: TEM image of formulation F6 (Scale size = 50nm)

Figure 2: TEM image of formulation F8 (Scale size = 20nm)

X-RAY DIFFRACTION (XRD)

X-ray diffraction (XRD) is a popular analytical technique which has been used for the analysis of both molecular and crystal structures, qualitative identification of various compounds, quantitative resolution of chemical species, measuring the degree of crystallinity, isomorphous substitutions, particle sizes. When X-ray light reflects on any crystal, it leads to the formation of many diffraction patterns, and the patterns reflect the physico-chemical characteristics of the crystal structures. Each material has a unique diffraction beam which can define and identify it by comparing the diffracted beams with the reference database in the Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards (JCPDS) library.[16][27][28]

The XRD pattern of Silver Nitrate (Figure 3) shows several sharp and intense diffraction peaks, indicating its highly crystalline structure. These peaks represent the ordered crystal lattice of the precursor material and serve as a reference before the nanoparticle synthesis process.

The XRD results of F6 and F8 confirm that Curcumin effectively reduced Silver Nitrate to form crystalline Silver Nanoparticles, as indicated by the characteristic peak at $2\theta \approx 38^\circ$, corresponding to the (111) plane of metallic silver). The broad peak indicates the formation of nanosized particles, and the peaks are consistent with the face-centered cubic structure of silver reported in JCPDS File No. 04-0783. The XRD patterns of the two formulations are shown in Figures 4 and 5, where F8 exhibited sharper and more intense peaks than F6, reflecting higher crystallinity and more stable nanoparticle formation.

Figure 3: XRD pattern of silver nitrate (AgNO₃)

Figure 4: XRD pattern of formulation F6

Figure 5: XRD pattern of formulation F8

FORMULATION OF TOPICAL DOSAGE FORMS

A petrolatum-based ointment was formulated by combining TF1 with 1% Cur-Ag NPs to achieve therapeutic effectiveness. Chlorobutanol (0.50%) was added as a preservative and BHT (0.10%) as an antioxidant to enhance stability. Mineral oil (5%) improved spreadability and emollient properties, while white petrolatum was used as the base to make up the final formulation. A detailed list of the formulation (TF1) components is shown in Table 5.

A PEG-based ointment (TF2) was formulated using 1% Cur-Ag NPs as the active component. Polyethylene glycol 1450 (40.5%) provided the solid base, while PEG 300 was added in sufficient quantity to make up of the final formulation. Table 6 summarizes the composition of the formulation (TF2).

A cream formulation (TF3) was prepared using 1% Cur-Ag NPs as the active ingredient. Disodium EDTA (0.10%) enhanced stability, while cetyl alcohol (5%) and stearic acid (2%) acted as emulsifying and consistency agents. Isopropyl myristate (5%) improved skin penetration, and Tween 80 (2%) stabilized the emulsion. Propylene glycol (5%) and glycerin (5%) served as humectants. Glyceryl monostearate (1%) supported emulsion structure, phenoxyethanol (1%) acted as a preservative, and BHT (0.10%) functioned as an antioxidant. Water was added to make up the final formulation. The components for formulation (TF3) details are listed in Table 7.

A gel formulation (TF4) was prepared using 1% Cur-Ag NPs as the active ingredient. Disodium EDTA (0.1%) was included to enhance stability, while propylene glycol (7%) and glycerin (5%) acted as humectants. Phenoxyethanol (1%) served as a preservative and BHT (0.1%) as an antioxidant. Carbomer homopolymer (0.5%) was used as the gelling agent, and sodium hydroxide was added q.s. to adjust the pH to 7–7.5. Purified water was used as the base and added to make up the final formulation. The detailed composition for formulation (TF4) is presented in Table 8.

Table 5: Compositions of Petrolatum based Ointment

Ingredients	Petrolatum based Ointment
	TF1
CU loaded Ag NPs	1%
Cholorobutanol	0.50%
BHT	0.10%
Mineral oil	5%
White petrolatum	q.s to 100%

Table 6: Compositions of PEG based Ointment

Ingredients	PEG based Ointment
	TF2
CU loaded Ag NPs	1%
PEG 1450	40.5%
PEG 300	q.s to 100%

Table 7: Compositions of Cream

Ingredients	Cream
	TF3
CU loaded Ag NPs	1%
Disodium EDTA	0.10%
Cetyl alcohol	5%
Stearic acid	2%
Isopropyl myristate	5%
Tween 80	2%
Propylene glycol	5%
Glycerin	5%
Glyceryl monostearate	1%
Phenoxyethanol	1%
BHT	0.10%
Water	q.s to 100%

Table 8: Compositions of Gel

Ingredients	Gel
	TF4
CU loaded Ag NPs	1%
Disodium EDTA	0.1%
Propylene glycol	7%
Glycerin	5%
Phenoxyethanol	1%
BHT	0.1%
Water	q.s to 100%
Carbomer homopolymer	0.5%
Sodium hydroxide	q.s to pH 7 – 7.5

pH EVALUATION OF TOPICAL DOSAGE FORMS

The pH of the cream and gel formulations was determined using a calibrated digital pH meter. Prior to each measurement, the instrument was standardized using buffer solutions of pH 4.0, 7.0, and 10.0. Approximately 1 g of each formulation, including the drug-loaded sample, was accurately weighed and dispersed in 25 mL of deionized water, followed by thorough mixing to ensure uniformity before measurement.

According to previous studies, cream formulations tend to exhibit a slightly more acidic pH compared to the natural skin pH, whereas gel formulations generally show pH values closer to that of normal skin [29]. In a separate study, the pH of topical formulations immediately after preparation was reported to range between 5.72 and 6.03, which lies within an acceptable range. Additionally, an optimal pH range of 5.5–7.0 is considered suitable for gel formulations to ensure skin compatibility and stability [30].

Formulations F1–F4 were assessed for appearance and pH to determine their suitability for topical use are shown in table 9. All were homogeneous, stable, and free from phase separation or foreign particles. pH was not measured for the ointments (TF1 and TF2) due to their non-aqueous nature. The cream (TF3) showed a pH of 5.12, close to skin pH, while the gel (TF4) had a near-neutral pH of 7.21, indicating good compatibility. Overall, the formulations demonstrated acceptable physicochemical properties for topical application.

Table 9: Description and pH

Batch No.	Formulation Type	Description	Observed pH
TF1	Ointment	Homogenous, without phase separation and free from foreign particles	NA
TF2	Ointment	Homogenous, without phase separation and free from foreign particles	NA
TF3	Cream	Homogenous, without phase separation and free from foreign particles	5.12
TF4	Gel	Homogenous, without phase separation and free from foreign particles	7.21

RHEOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION

Rheology studies material flow (yield stress) and deformation, and is essential for evaluating the spreadability of semisolid formulations. Yield stress, inversely related to spreadability, is measured using a rheometer via flow curve modeling or amplitude sweep tests at the end of the linear viscoelastic region (LVR).

Rheological measurements were performed using an Anton Paar MCR 302 rheometer with a PP25/S geometry at $25 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ and a gap of 0.200 mm. Flow curves were obtained over a shear rate range of $0.001\text{--}1000\text{ s}^{-1}$. Amplitude sweep tests were conducted at 1 s^{-1} over a strain range of 0.1–50% to determine viscoelastic properties and yield stress.

The formulations exhibited typical shear-thinning behavior, characterized by a decrease in viscosity with increasing shear rate are shown in figure 6. Similar trends have been reported in stress-controlled rheological studies, where viscosity decreases with increasing shear stress due to progressive disruption of the internal structure. Despite differences in control mode, both approaches describe the same fundamental flow behavior of semisolid systems.

Although the amplitude sweep in the present study was conducted under strain-controlled conditions, similar viscoelastic behavior has been reported in stress-controlled amplitude sweep measurements, where the storage modulus (G') remains constant within the linear viscoelastic region and decreases beyond the yield point due to structural breakdown [31].

Yield stress represents the minimum force required for a formulation to flow and spread, with lower values indicating easier spreadability. In previous studies, creams show low yield stress

(~3 Pa), while structured semisolids range from 30–150 Pa, indicating greater resistance to flow.[32]

The yield stress of the ointment formulations was 43.19 Pa (TF1) and 61.05 Pa (TF2), which was significantly higher than that of the cream (1.105 Pa, TF3) and gel (2.123 Pa, TF4), indicating a stronger internal structural network in the ointment base. The yield stress (Pa) of TF1–TF4 formulations is summarized in Table 10. Accordingly, the cream and gel exhibited easier spreadability, whereas the ointments showed comparatively lower spreadability due to their higher yield stress.

Figure 6: Flow curve (viscosity vs. shear rate) of TF1–TF4

Figure 7: Amplitude sweep curve (storage modulus G' vs. shear strain) of TF1–TF4

Table 10: Yield stress (Pa) of TF1–TF4 formulations

Formulations	TF1	TF2	TF3	TF4
Yield Stress (Tau value) (Pa)	43.19	61.05	1.105	2.123

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrates the nine formulations of Cur-Ag NPs (F1-F9) were synthesised and characterized. The UV-Visible spectra show an SPR peak in the 400–500 nm range confirm the successful formation of Cur-Ag nanoparticle in formulations(F1-F8), while except F9 did not show SPR peak in the 223nm. Based on the SPR Peak, PSD and Zeta potential finding, formulation F6 and F8 were identified as suitable formulations for further advanced structural characterization. TEM micrograph for formulation F6 and F8 revealed spherical nanoparticles with slight aggregation and well-defined spherical nanoparticles respectively. XRD analysis confirmed that curcumin effectively reduced silver nitrate to form crystalline silver nanoparticles, with F8 exhibiting higher crystallinity and greater stability than F6. All four formulations (TF1–TF4) were successfully developed with 1% Cur-Ag NPs, providing stable and suitable for topical application. Ointments TF1 and TF2 exhibited higher yield stress but lower spreadability, whereas cream TF3 and gel TF4 were easier to apply, reflecting formulation-dependent rheological properties. Further studies including in vivo evaluation would need to be conducted to assess their therapeutic potential.

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